
TEACHERS' EVALUATION AND USE OF TEACHER'S GUIDES IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSES

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ABSTRACT

Teacher's guides have not been sufficiently evaluated by professionals in ELT to date. The purpose of this study was to investigate the use of widely used teacher's guides and to evaluate their usefulness. The research was a qualitative one and the data were collected via the observation of 15 English language classes and interviewing 17 English teachers at College of Ferdowsi University in Mashhad, a city in northeastern Iran. Teachers' use of and their ideas about the teacher's guides were then explored. The books taught by these teachers were *Interchange (Third Edition)*, *Rising Star*, and *Ready for FCE*. It became evident that the use of teacher's guides is different among teachers. Although teachers used teacher's guides differently, they all wanted better, more resourceful ones. Finally, the results were discussed within a foreign language teaching context, and suggestions were given for future research.

KEYWORDS: Teacher's guides, English language teaching, Classroom observation, Interview

INTRODUCTION

One of the aims of the educational system in Iran is to provide students with proficiency in English in order to acquire knowledge in different fields of science as a way of exchanging knowledge with other countries. Obviously, the content of English textbooks taught in schools, universities, and private language institutes has a significant association with learning.

Materials used in language classrooms are one of the main tools in teaching and so there must be a framework for analyzing and evaluating the language teaching materials (Littlejohn, 1992). Textbooks are widely used in language institutes and they have become an important part of English teaching profession. These books are usually accompanied by teacher's manuals and teacher's guides which are aimed at helping teachers to manage the course. Evaluating these textbooks and teacher's guides with close scrutiny is pivotal both to language teaching and learning as it can help teachers and institutes choose better books. As Williams (1983) states, if the teachers stipulate the weak and strong points of the books they teach, they can compensate for the weaknesses. There is a wide range of articles which propose checklists for evaluation of textbooks and their activities (e.g., Crandall and Basturkmen, 2004; Davies, 2006; Duff, Wong, and Early, 2002). There are also many studies which have employed an empirical approach to textbook evaluation (e.g., Ali, 1983; Al-Jaser, 1988; Ereksoussy, 1993; Nitta and Gardner, 2005; Thein, 2006). However, as Coleman (1985) states, teacher's guides seem to be ignored by professionals in ELT. Although teacher's guides play a very important role in teaching, they have been somewhat neglected and little attention has been paid to them. Writers who have evaluated materials have ignored teacher's guides or have written about them very briefly (Cunningsworth and Kusel, 1991). According to Cunningsworth and Kusel (1991), although teacher's guides are really important, they are not written scrupulously. Not surprisingly, therefore, the quality of teaching will be deteriorated if teacher's guides are inaccurate or of low quality. Coleman (1985) also points out that material reviews pay no attention to teacher's guides (as cited in Hemsley, 1997). Therefore, the present study sought to evaluate teacher's guides via English teachers' use and evaluation of them. Such evaluation would benefit not only teachers and students, but also curriculum developers as well as textbook designers.

Review of literature

Material evaluation is "the systematic appraisal of the value of materials in relation to their objectives and to the objectives of the learners using them. Evaluation can be pre-use and therefore focused on predictions of potential value. It can be whilst-use and therefore focused on awareness and description of what the learners are

actually doing whilst the materials are being used. And it can be post-use and therefore focused on analysis of what happened as a result of using the materials” (Tomlinson, 1998, p. xi).

Why should we evaluate teachers' guides?

If teachers can evaluate teacher's guides, they will be able to select a textbook easier, becoming more aware of the extent to which the teacher's guide can help them use the textbook more effectively. Moreover, their advantages and drawbacks will come to the surface and, as a result, the teacher's guide can be improved. Evaluating teacher's guides may also encourage teachers to develop their autonomy (Gearing, 1999).

As Coleman (1985) has pointed out, if teacher's guides do not satisfy teachers' needs, they are not guiding teachers in reality. Teacher's guides need evaluation because the aims, values and methods are dealt with in them in an explicit manner (as cited in Hemsley, 1997). The teacher must be able to evaluate certain quantitative and qualitative elements of the textbook, teacher's manual, and other accompanying materials (Skierso, 1991). Coleman (1985) claims that the main criteria for evaluating a teacher's guide are the assumptions which it is based on. These assumptions include attitudes toward language, language learning and methodology. They also include teachers' attitudes towards educational issues and the extent to which teachers have the ability and willingness to deal with ambiguity and incompleteness in teacher's guides (as cited in Cunningsworth and Kusel, 1991).

An ideal teacher's guide

According to Harmer (2007) a teacher's guide is the manual that normally comes with the coursebook and is full of ideas and notes about how to use the material. If the teacher's guide has a wide range of users, then, the teacher with the least training, knowledge, and confidence should be considered (Cunningsworth and Kusel, 1991). Cunningsworth (1995) contends that teacher's guides should satisfy the needs of their users as much as possible and they should be as flexible as possible at the same time.

A good standard of teaching will be achieved if teacher's guides provide information about language, help on the way of teaching, and a rationale for the course (Cunningsworth and Kusel, 1991). Fillmore and Snow (2002) recommend that all teachers should have the necessary knowledge about the language. In other words, the knowledge of linguistics is pivotal for teachers (Attardo and Brown, 2005), because the lack of linguistic knowledge hinders teachers from problem anticipation making the teacher unable to present the new language clearly and efficiently (Thornbury, 1997). If teachers do not know about the language, they will feel anxious (Andrews and McNeil, 2005). Students expect their teachers to explain grammar concepts clearly. The teachers must know how and when to use them. Students want their teachers to know the differences between the formal and informal language. The students also expect their teachers to correct their pronunciation and intonation mistakes (Harmer, 2007). As Akbulut (2007) notes, teachers not only need to do things but also they need to know *how* to do things.

A teacher's guide should help teachers use the textbook more effectively. It should also tell the teachers what values are embodied in the textbook and relate these values to teachers' opinions about principles of teaching. Moreover, it should state the aim of the course as well as the level and age of the learners it is designed for (Cunningsworth and Kusel, 1991). According to Cunningsworth and Kusel (1991), teacher's guides which give explicit suggestions for planning a lesson and conducting it satisfy the needs of a wide range of users. Teachers should be aware of sequencing language activities so that they can use them more effectively (Chastain, 1988). If the teacher's guide provides such guidance, it will help a lot. In addition, a good teacher's guide gives hints on how the course will be most effective and provides detailed plans for teaching and the keys to exercises (Cunningsworth, 1995).

It is taken for granted that culture cannot be separated from language (Chastain, 1988). Therefore, the basic information that helps one understand the second language culture must be given to learners by the teacher. If teachers are not equipped with such knowledge, they cannot teach it. Teachers who have not spent much time abroad are not aware of the foreign culture. Even natives who have been far away for years don't know the changes that have taken place in the culture. Put it another way, teachers need some information about the problems and difficulties that might be encountered when they are teaching cultural points (Cunningsworth and Kusel, 1991). A good teacher's guide will provide teachers with sufficient information on cultural points.

The teacher's guides should also provide some regular tests for evaluating the students' progress (Cunningsworth and Kusel, 1991; Cunningsworth, 1995). As Brophy and Good (1986) declare, teachers are expected to provide their students with assignments at a suitable level of challenge (as cited in Chastain, 1988); so if a teacher's guide provide suitable assignments, teachers who are less experienced in language testing may benefit most.

Cunningsworth and Kusel (1991) state that, the teacher's guide must contribute positively in raising the motivation of learners, as motivation is an important factor in learning a language. Chastain, (1988) correctly claims that students' attention span is not very long and they get bored if activities last for more than 10-15 minutes. The teacher must provide the class with a variety of activities. Not only the activity but also the content and theme of it must change. Variety is a necessity and teacher's guides should provide this variety. Variety makes a lesson interesting (Bailey and Celce-Murcia, 1979). If activities are various, students will learn the point without being bored. However, as Cunningsworth and Kusel (1991) and Cunningsworth (1995) put, teacher's guides should be user friendly, i.e. easy to use, and their language should be comprehensible for nonnative teachers. The explanations must be simple, clear and intelligible.

Why are teachers' guides necessary?

In the project done for improving educational quality by Moulton (1994), teachers' use of materials was taken into account. It was found that teachers differ in the use of materials and that they use the print material differently. Variation was also observed in teachers' use of teacher's guides. Some teachers used the suggestions a lot while others rarely used them.

According to Gearing (1999) in countries where teachers don't have any formal teacher training courses, it is important for teachers to be able to evaluate teacher's guides. As Richards (1993) notes, in many parts of the world teacher's guides are the primary teaching resources as there are no formal teacher training courses. Hemsley (1997) states that if suitable teacher's guides can be found, training budgets will be reduced and teachers will try to conform to teacher's guides rather than oppose them. Cunningsworth and Kusel (1991) believe that teacher's guides are very important for teachers, especially for beginners who have little or no experience of teaching as well as for those teachers who are not proficient in the English language. Bullough, Knowles and Crow (1991) also refer to teachers' concerns about class management, methods and explanations, and relationship with students. As teachers gain experience their need for information on class management and planning lessons becomes less. Experienced teachers write more realistic lesson plans (as cited in Akbulut, 2007). Berliner (2004) claims that it takes 3-5 years to gain competence in teaching, but acquiring high skills as a teacher needs about 5-7 years of teaching. When textbooks are used to teach English as a foreign language in a country, teacher's guides become even more important than textbooks because the teacher in these countries heavily depends on teacher's guides for methodological guidance, and linguistic and cultural information (Cunningsworth and Kusel, 1991). It has been observed that some nonnative teachers lack the necessary linguistic skills in teaching (Bailey, 2006); therefore, teacher's guides may be helpful in this regard (Williams, 1983).

Cunningsworth and Kusel (1991) count five functions for teacher's guides as follows:

1. Teacher's guides can function as providers of information about the general goal of teaching material and describing the methodological rationale.
2. Teacher's guides can help teachers develop teaching skills.
3. Teacher's guides help the teacher in understanding the way the course material is structured and the contribution of each lesson to the whole course.
4. Teacher's guides may offer help on the practical use of the material.
5. Teacher's guides provide the linguistic and cultural information for teachers.

Criticizing the ideas against teacher's guides

Some scholars believe that teacher's guides and textbooks deskill teachers as most of the teachers' decisions are based on these materials. They believe that these teacher's guides trivialize teachers' role while teaching is preplanned by others (Richards, 1993; Richards and Renandya, 2002). Similarly, Littlejohn (1992) contends that

materials will only deskill teachers when they are based on the belief that the teacher cannot plan a curriculum. However, as Hemsley (1997) states, although teacher's guides may deskill experienced teachers, they do empower untrained, nonnative teachers and, as a result, do more good than harm. It may be the case that there is incoherence when novice teachers choose their own materials (Crawford, 2002). Cunningsworth (1995) also notes that it is the teacher who makes the ultimate decision informed by the feedback from the students and the help of the teacher's guide. In other words, a good teacher's guide will help the teacher be more innovative and creative, and will avoid stereotyped teaching.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to examine teachers' use of teacher's guides in Iran and whether these guides need any changes so that they can help teachers more. The titles of the books are *Interchange (Third Edition)*, *Rising Star*, and *Ready for FCE*.

METHODOLOGY

Participants

The participants were 15 teachers teaching at the College of Ferdowsi University of Mashhad. They consisted of 5 male and 10 female teachers whose age ranged from 21 to 37. The teachers' educational background was as follows: Four teachers had their BAs in TEFL and five had their BAs in English literature; two were BA students in English Literature; one had her MA in English Literature; and the other three were MA students in TEFL. Two teachers who taught specialized courses (e.g., FCE) were also interviewed. One of them had her MA in TEFL and the other one was an MA student in TEFL. Their teaching experience ranged from 2 to 11 years. Most of them had an experience of about 4 to 6 years, however. They all taught mixed classes in College of Ferdowsi University of Mashhad.

Instrumentation

Observation and interview were used for data collection. Then the collected data was analyzed to see if any pattern would be observed.

The books taught at the institute at the time of data collection were *Interchange (Third Edition)* (Richards, Hall, and Proctor, 2005), *Rising Star* (Prodromou, 2000) and *Ready for FCE* (Noris, 2008). In six of the observed classes *Interchange 2* was taught (in one of them the teacher taught reading unit 6 and the first two pages of unit 7, in another one the middle 2 pages of unit 7 were taught and in another one the middle three pages of unit 7 were taught. In one class the first three pages of unit 8 were taught. In one other class the middle three pages of unit 14 were taught and in the last one the teacher taught the first three pages of unit 15). In three of the observed classes *Interchange Intro* was taught (in two classes the teachers taught the first three pages of unit 7 and in the other one the teacher taught the last three pages of unit 16). In five classes *Interchange 1* was taught (in two of them the three middle pages of unit 7 were taught, in one of them the first three pages of unit 14 were taught, in another one reading unit 15 was taught with the first two pages of unit 16 and in the last one the three middle pages of unit 16 were taught) and in the last class *Rising Star* was taught (the grammar part in unit 4). Two other teachers who taught *Rising Star* were also interviewed and their ideas on the book and the accompanying teacher's book were asked.

The *Interchange intro, 1* and *2* were divided into two parts and the learners were supposed to study 8 units in each semester. *Rising Star* was divided into four parts and the teachers were supposed to teach four units in each semester. Each session, one skill was usually considered in *Rising Star*.

Procedure

The data was collected in a week using classroom observation and teacher interview. Fifteen classes were observed and all the activities teachers did were recorded. Next, the written data were compared to the guidelines and different parts in the teacher's guide to see if any particular pattern could be observed.

Having observed the classes, the researchers interviewed the teachers. The teachers were asked to give some information on the years of their experience and their age. They were also asked to talk about the degree to which they used the teacher's guide and the parts they used more often. Their opinions on the positive and negative points of the teacher's guide were inquired as well. Then they talked of the points that needed to be changed as well as about the features of an ideal teacher's guide. At the end, they were asked whether the degree

of using the teacher's guide had become less or more as they had gained experience. Their answers to these questions were also recorded to see if we could come up with any pattern.

The teachers' ideas about the teacher's guides, their use of the teacher's guide, their experience, and their teaching ability were then compared.

RESULTS

The data reported here is gathered from observations of 15 classes and interviews done with the teachers after class observations. Two other teachers who taught FCE levels were also involved in the interview.

The observations

No use of the teacher's guide

The teacher was a 25-year-old woman whose teaching experience was 6 years. It was an intensive class which was held 5 days a week. The students were studying the second half of *Interchange 2* (Unit 14).

The teacher started with asking questions about the lesson taught the previous day. The grammar focus was taught before (although in the teacher's guide it is taught after the conversation part) and the teacher asked the students to give some examples on what they might do with the new structure (they had learned the modals and adverbs used for talking about probability).

The teacher started teaching the conversation. She asked her students to listen with their books closed and give a summary with the learned structures. Then she read it herself and attracted the students' attention to the grammatical points and collocations used in the conversation. As the conversation was about Indians and their body language, the teacher started asking questions about India and Indian movies and Indian culture. She gave her students some information on Indian culture.

The conversation was repeated and the teacher asked 3 students to replace the words of probability used in the conversation with other structures they had learned the previous session.

The teacher didn't pay attention to the sequence of activities. The listening which followed the grammar part was done the previous session and the students had written it. One of them read his own writing and the teacher commented on his mistakes. Then the new vocabulary and the collocations were explained.

The teacher explained the pronunciation points, and then she asked students to bring real life examples.

The teacher taught the grammatical points completely and gave lots of examples. She explained each point carefully and related all she taught to real life situations. In all activities she asked her students to use the new grammatical points and the new vocabulary.

When the teacher was interviewed, she said that she used the teacher's guides when she had had no experience but she did not use it anymore because it was monotonous and there was no variety in the suggested activities. She believed that teacher's guides are necessary for beginning teachers and also for those with no creativity.

Modified use of the teacher's guide

The teacher was a 27-year-old woman with a teaching experience of 6.5 years. The class was held 2 days a week. The students were studying the first half of *Interchange Intro* (Unit 7).

The teacher reviewed the previous lesson before doing the workbook. After doing the workbook, she reviewed the tenses she had taught her students as this was the first semester they were learning English and they had problems with tenses. The teacher then started teaching the conversation. She asked the students to cover the text of the conversation and started asking questions about the picture, using the words and grammatical structures they had mastered.

Next, she asked the students to close their books, and explained the key words with drawings and realia (e.g., she explained the meaning of *view* by talking about the class and its view). Then she wrote a question on the board and asked the students to listen and answer the question. Next, the students repeated the conversation with their books closed while the teacher explained the new words. Moreover, the teacher tried to exemplify the grammatical points which appeared in the conversation. Although the grammar focus (wh-questions with do and does) followed the conversation, it was taught prior to practicing the conversation. The conversation was

repeated once more with the books open followed by a pair work. The teacher monitored the students while they were doing the pair work; they were then asked to repeat the words which they found difficult to pronounce. Later on, the teacher asked the learners to do the exercises in the book and gave them some extra sentences to turn into yes/no and wh- questions. After that, the teacher wrote some questions on the board and assigned a role play. When it was finished, the students changed partners and reported whatever their partner had said for their new partner. Then all of the students were asked to report for the class their information about their first partner. For starting the word power section, which was about furniture, the teacher drew a picture of a house on the board with different rooms and asked the students what things they usually put in each room. The students answered, in this way, some furniture was introduced. Then the students opened their books, listened to the CD, and repeated the words.

When the teacher was interviewed she said that her use of the teacher's guides had become less than before but that she still used it. She believed that she could find good ideas for teaching a few parts and that she used the answer keys. She suggested that there should be a greater variety of activities and some cultural information in the teacher's guide.

Complete use of the teacher's guide with no modification

The teacher was a 28-year-old woman whose teaching experience was 3 years. The class was held 2 days a week. The students were studying the first half of *Interchange 2* (Unit 7).

The teacher used the teacher's guide in the class. The teacher started to teach the word power part. She read the instructions and asked the students to do the task individually and add two more words when they finished. Even the meanings of the words that were given to the students were the ones provided by the teacher's guide. The words whose meanings were not provided by the teacher's guide were unfamiliar to the teacher. The answers were checked.

A group work was then assigned just the same as the teacher's guide had suggested. The teacher explained the words presented in the teacher's guide, and asked the students to discuss the questions in small groups.

The teacher went on to the listening part. First she asked the students what the title of the listening meant and she provided the students with the answer that the teacher's guide had provided for the question. She read the questions and asked the students to guess the answers and then played the audio program and elicited the answers. The answers were checked. Then they listened to the second part of the listening and answered the questions.

The conversation was also performed in the same way. The teacher meticulously followed the activities in the teacher's guide and, when she was teaching the grammar section, she didn't even try to give some new examples or to explain the points carefully for the students.

When the teacher was interviewed, she claimed that she used the teacher's guides in only a few cases. She believed that it was not well written, yet she asserted that she did use the answer keys.

DISCUSSION ON THE FINDINGS

The degree of using the teacher's guide

Out of the fifteen teachers observed, two of them did not use teacher's guides at all. One of them tried to be creative and match her teaching to the level of the students. She related all the materials to students' lives. When she was teaching body language in different cultures, for example, she asked her students if they have ever had problems understanding body language while giving some information on her own experience. The other one did not even check the answers with the teacher's guide and this caused problems when the topics of the book dealt with general knowledge. For instance, he could not answer the questions which were asked about geography; therefore, she asked the students to find the answers themselves.

Seven teachers used teacher's guides 30 to 60 percent of the time. They tried to use the helpful points which made the class better. For example, they used interesting warm up questions, and some useful tasks as well as the answer keys.

Four teachers used the teacher's guide 60 to 70 percent of the whole class time. They used the activities in the teacher's guides while paying attention to the feedback they received from their students. As a case in point, if their students did not understand a grammatical point, they explained it more and in new ways. They did not rely on the activities alone.

Two teachers relied on the teacher's guide heavily and only practiced the points that were included in them. They did not try to change the activities based on the feedback they received from the students. They did not even try to give better explanations for the words their students didn't understand.

The teachers also believed that some activities could not be used in the Iranian context as they were not culturally appropriate. The activities that were suggested for heterogeneous classes were also useless.

The teachers who had the experience of teaching both general and specialized courses believed that their use of teacher's guides was more when they were teaching specialized courses (e.g., FCE) because teaching such courses is done with the aim of preparing students for special exams and the teacher's guides for such books help them guide students toward the exam better. They also believed that the students' needs were more similar at that level.

Teaching experience and teacher's use of the teacher's guides

Teachers with an experience of two years and less relied heavily on the teacher's guide and tried to follow all the steps although they changed a few parts.

Teachers with more experience put the activities provided by the teacher's guide and their experience together. They knew the areas students would be likely to encounter problems so they focused on those areas more and provided students with extra exercises. They also believed that if teacher's guides were improved, they could be more helpful. Besides, they were looking for a various range of activities in the teacher's guides.

However, some exceptions were observed: A teacher with an experience of two and a half years did not use the teacher's guide at all, and believed that it was not useful. On the other hand, there were also two teachers with more than four years of teaching experience who heavily relied on the teacher's guide.

Nonetheless, almost all teachers agreed that their use of teacher's guide had become less in the passage of time because of the experience they had gained. These teachers stated that when they had started teaching for the first time they were in need of the teacher's guide because of lack of experience, but now they used it less considering the class environment. Only one teacher believed that her use of the teacher's guide had become more making her more successful than the time she ignored it. She believed that her lack of teaching experience together with ignoring the teacher's guide caused lots of problems for her and now the guidance provided by the teacher's guide helped her a lot.

What do teachers need most?

Nearly all teachers agreed that tape scripts and keys were used by them a lot. Most teachers also talked of their need for better guidance on grammar and ways of teaching different points. The teachers also believed that lack of variety in the teacher's guide makes teaching boring. They believed that if some variety were added, the teacher's guide would be more useful. The teachers looked for better and more interesting activities; they believed that there should be a number of different and alternative activities in teacher's guides so that they could selectively choose the activities which were suitable for the specific cultural context. They also believed that if teacher's guides were written in a better way with more cultural and linguistic information, they would be more useful.

The use of teacher's guides and success in teaching

The researchers observed that those teachers who used both the teacher's guide and their own creativity, and those who paid attention to learners' weak points and demands were the most successful teachers. When the teachers' efficiency was double checked with the supervisor of the institute, it became evident that those who put the activities in the teacher's guide and creativity together were the most successful ones judged by both the supervisor and their own students. The supervisor and the students believed that these teachers were very active and their classes were not tiring, they were so exact, and paid attention to all the points in the book. Having been interviewed after the semester came to its end, the students contended that they had learned much in the

previous semester, and that their scores were higher than those of their peers who were studying at the same level in other classes.

CONCLUSION

The results of the present study revealed that the teachers differed in their use of teacher's guides. Some overused it, some did not use it at all, and the rest preferred to modify it. Interestingly, even experienced teachers and those who did not use the teacher's guides pointed to the need for better, more reliable ones. They also suggested that adding variety would make the teacher's guides more useful. Having compared the efficiency of the teachers, the researchers found out that those teachers who modified the activities proposed by the teacher's guide based on the feedback they received from their students were most successful. It can be inferred from this fact that the teacher's guides need modification and it is the teacher who should decide which parts to use.

To bring the confines of the research within bounds amenable to study, certain delimitations had to be imposed on it. Firstly, the observer was a colleague of the teachers and this caused anxiety. Secondly, the observer's effect was present. Thirdly, only teachers in one institute were observed; if the study is done in other contexts, it might yield different results.

Therefore, further research is needed to verify the nature of teacher's guides using other measures of evaluation and across other nations and cultural contexts, in order to establish if similar findings hold in other settings and contexts. Other researchers might also conduct studies to suggest areas of improvement in the teacher's guides.

REFERENCES

- Akbulut, Y. (2007). Exploration of the beliefs of novice language teachers at the first year of their teaching endeavors. *Selçuk University Journal of Social Sciences Institute*, 17.
- Ali, F. M. (1983). *Evaluating the English language textbook studied at the second grade intermediate schools in Saudi Arabia*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, Umm Al-Qura University, Makkah, Saudi Arabia.
- Aljaser, A. M. (1989). *An analysis of the English language textbooks taught at the first year boy and girls' secondary schools: A comparative study*. Unpublished MA thesis, King Saud University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.
- Andrews, S., & McNeill, A. (2005). Knowledge about language and the good language teacher. In N. Bartels (Ed.), *Applied linguistics and language teacher education*. New York: Springer Science+Buisness Media, Inc.
- Attardo, S., & Brown, S. (2005). What's the use of linguistics? Pre-service English teachers' beliefs towards language use and variation. In N. Bartels (Ed.), *Applied linguistics and language teacher education* (pp. 91-102). New York: Springer Science+Buisness Media, Inc.
- Bailey, K. M. (2006). *Language teacher supervision: A case-based approach*. USA: Cambridge University Press.
- Bailey, K. M., & Celce-Murcia, M. (1979). Classroom skills for ESL teachers. In M. Celce-Murcia, & L. McIntosh (Eds.), *Teaching English as a second or foreign language* (pp. 315-331). Rowley, MA: Newbury House.
- Berliner, D. C. (2004). Describing the behavior and documenting the accomplishments of expert teachers. *Bulletin of Science, Technology and Society*, 24, 200-212.
- Bullough, R. V., & Baughman, K. (1995). Changing contexts and expertise in teaching: First-year teacher after seven years. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 11(5), 461-477.
- Chastain, K. (1988). *Developing second-language skills: theory and practice* (3rd ed.). USA: Harcourt Brace Jovanovich.
- Crandall, E., & Basturkmen, H. (2004). Evaluating pragmatics-focused materials. *ELT Journal*, 58(1), 38-49.

- Crawford, J. (2002). The role of materials in the language classroom: finding the balance. In J. C Richards, & W. A. Renandya (Eds.), *Methodology in language teaching: an anthology of current practice*. (pp. 80-92). USA: Cambridge University Press.
- Cunningworth, A. (1995). *Choosing your coursebook*. Great Britain: The Bath Press.
- Cunningworth, A., & Kusel, P. (1991). Evaluating teachers' guides. *ELT Journal*, 45(2), 128-139.
- Davies, A. (2006). What do learners really want from their EFL courses? *ELT Journal*, 60(1), 3-12.
- Duff, P.A., Wong, P., & Early, M. (2002). Language learning for work and life: The linguistic socialization of immigrant Canadians seeking careers in healthcare. *The Modern Language Journal*, 86(3), 397-422.
- Eriksoussy, Z. M. (1993). *Evaluating the English language textbook studied at the first year intermediate schools in Saudi Arabia*. Unpublished MA thesis, King Saud University. Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.
- Fillmore, L. W., & Snow, C. E. (2002). What teachers need to know about language. In C. A. Adger, C. E. Snow, & D. Christian (Eds.), *What teachers need to know about language* (pp. 7-54). McHenry, IL and Washington, DC: Delta Systems, and Center for Applied Linguistics.
- Gearing, K. (1999). Helping less-experienced teachers of English to evaluate teachers' guides. *ELT Journal*, 53, 122-127.
- Harmer, J. (2007). *How to teach English*. UK: Longman.
- Hemsley, M. (1997). The evaluation of teachers' guides design and application. *ELT Journal*, 3(1), 72-83.
- Littlejohn, A. P. (1992). Why are ELT materials the way they are? Lancaster, Lancaster University: 299.
- Moulton, J. (1994). How do teachers use textbooks and other print materials? A review of literature. The Improving Educational Quality Project, South Africa, 1994.
- Nitta, R., & Gardner, S. (2005). Consciousness-raising and practice in ELT coursebooks. *ELT Journal*, 59(1), 3-13.
- Noris, R. (2008). *Ready for FCE*. Oxford: Macmillan Publishers, Ltd.
- Prodromou, L. (2000). *Rising star*. Oxford: Macmillan Publishers, Ltd.
- Richards, J. C. (1993). Beyond the text book: The role of commercial materials in language teaching. *RELC Journal*, 24(1), 1-14.
- Richards, J. C., Hall, J., & Proctor, S. (2005). *Interchange (3rd ed)*. UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Richards, J. C., & Renandya, W. A. (2002). *Methodology in language teaching: An anthology of current practice*. USA: Cambridge University Press.
- Skierso, A. (1991). Textbook selection and evaluation. In Celce-Murcia, M. (Ed.), *Teaching English as a second or foreign language*. Boston: Heinle & Heinle.
- Thein, N. (2006) *Evaluating the suitability and effectiveness of three English coursebooks at Myanmar Institute of Technology*. Unpublished MA thesis, University of Thailand, Thailand.
- Thornbury, S. (1997). *About language: Tasks for teachers of English*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Tomlinson, B. (1998). Comments on Part C. In Tomlinson, B. (ed), *Materials development in language teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Williams, D. (1983). Developing criteria for textbook evaluation. *ELT Journal*, 37(3), 251-255.

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